

Effect of Strategic Change on Banks Performance; Evidence from Kenya

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Abstract:

The main objectives of the study were to determine the effect of strategic change on bank performance in Kenya. The study was informed by Organizational Life Cycle Theory, Contingency theory, three-step change theory and Lippitt's phases of change theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The total population was 255 head of departments drawn from 25 banks within Nairobi CBD. Stratified and random sampling techniques were used to select 119 respondents. The study used the questionnaire in data collection. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistical measures such as, mean, standard deviation and variance to give a glimpse of the general trend. In addition, inferential statistics which included Pearson correlation and multiple regression were used to test the relationship. The findings indicate organization leadership style change, and employee-training change has significant effect on bank performance. The study concludes that employee training change is of essence in improving bank performance. Therefore, there is need for banks managers to emphasize on employee training so that they can develop the appropriate knowledge and skills to work efficiently, and achieve bank objectives

Keywords: Leadership Style, Bank Performance, Employee-Training, Strategic Change

Introduction

Organization performance is very essential to management and other stakeholders such as shareholders, debt holders and the government as it is an outcome which has been achieved by an individual or a group of individuals in an organization related to its authority and responsibility in achieving the goal legally, not against the law, and conforming to the morale and ethic (Iswatia & Anshoria, 2007). Increased competition, rapid change, reduced resources and mounting employee expectations, have all combined in such a way that organizations are being expected to achieve more out of less (Neely *et al.*, 2006). However, in the competitive market environment, financial institutions seeking to improve their performance cannot simply rely on quality, but also on change.

Recognizing the need for change and leading organizations through that change is one of the most challenging for any leadership. Change is the only constant in today's life – for individuals and organizations. Strategic change should be effective, for example have the ability to move freely, have the ability to influence others, and directing the working forces in the target systems and administrative units (Harem, 2004). Balogun & Hailey (2008) argue that all organizations are currently undergoing some type of change.

Many of these change programs arise from management such as culture change, business process engineering, empowerment and total quality. For banks to improve on their performance and continuously evolving business environment, it must be able to successfully manage the change which is as a necessity. Even though there has not been consensus as to the framework for organizational strategic change and bank performance, there seems to be an agreement that change, management improves bank performance (Balogun & Hailey 2004). Most organizational managers today would agree that change has become a constant phenomenon which must be attended to and managed properly if an organization is to survive. Changes in technology, the marketplace, information systems, the global economy, social values, workforce demographics, and the political environment all have a significant effect on the processes, products and services produced. The culmination of these forces has resulted in an external environment that is dynamic, unpredictable, demanding and often devastating to those organizations which are unprepared or unable to respond (Burnes, 2004).

Strategic change has become an increasingly pervasive phenomenon in both business and human service organizations due to forces such as globalization and technology (Walumbwa, 2008). Strategic change is seen as a necessary concept for organizations to compete in the ever changing and competitive business environment. Most of organization has experienced change. Yet despite organization's familiarity with change, success in implementation is relatively rare. It was estimated that 70% of strategic change initiatives fail completely (Kibwana, 2012). Among those deemed successful, 75% of them fail to achieve their intended result (Korir *et al*, 2012). Despite these low success rates, organizations still continue with the change managements in an attempt to adapt and respond to the changing economic conditions, technological innovations, customer and client expectations and a shifting workforce. It was estimated that 56% of organizations are undergoing three or more complex changes at one time or another (Kim, 2006) .

Studies have been conducted on strategic change for example Kibwana(2012) on strategic change practices at local authorities in the Coastal Province of Kenya. Mwirigi (2012) also studied management of strategic change by commercial banks in Kenya and Mutwiri (2012) on Strategic Management Practices at Kenya authority. However, while the above research outcome provides valuable insights on strategic change, they have not induced a clear effect of best strategic change practices on bank performance in Commercial banks in Kenya. Given the gaps poised by the above empirical studies, this study poses the research question: "what is the effect of strategic change on bank performance?". This study sought to answer the following questions; are there strategic change practices in commercial banks of Kenya? and does strategic change affect bank performance? thus, study hypothesized that:

H₀₁: Leadership Style Change has no significant effect on Bank Performance

H₀₂: Employee training change has no significant bank performance

Theoretical Framework

Organizational Life Cycle Theory by Queen (1983) focused on changes in organizational structure. According to life-cycle theory, change is imminent: that is, the developing entity has within it an underlying form, logic, program, or code that regulates the process of change and moves the entity from a given point of departure toward a subsequent end that is prefigured in the present state."(Anderew, 1995). As Mintzberg(1983) points out, "Each stage in organization life cycle is a cluster of attributes, or configurations in organizations"(Mintzberg,1984) and Queen mentions, "At least nine different models of organizational life cycles have been proposed, each of which emphasizes different factors to explain the changing characteristics of organizations over time."(Mintzberg, 1984). In order to cope with the complexity of organization attributes, organizational lifecycle models consider a limited set of organizational attributes. Although this makes it easier to track the changes and also to determine a boundary for each stage, the mutual relationship between different characteristics which indicates the change is not usually well described. The organizational life cycle theory is still a common concept to evaluate the firm's current status and the necessary steps for further development.

Change occurs in predictable patterns that can be characterized by developmental stages. According to Quinn und Cameron (1983, p. 33) "these stages are (1) sequential in nature, (2) occur as a hierarchical progression that is not easily reversed, and (3) involve a broad range of organizational activities and structures." Organizational life-cycle theories assume the characteristics of the environment and a multitude of organizational characteristics such as structure, strategy, control systems, decision-making styles and critical development areas to change as developmental stages progress. Independent contextual factors, such as the hostility of the industry an organization is operating in, are assumed to have only a limited influence on the strategic change of an organization. The dependent and independent variables will be summarized in the conceptual framework below:

Independent variable**Dependent variable**

Figure1: Conceptual framework

2000).

Empirical Review

Leadership Style Change on Bank performance

Leadership change is one of the key driving forces for improving bank performance. Leaders, as the key decision-makers, determine the acquisition, development, and deployment of organizational resources, the conversion of these resources into valuable products and services, and the delivery of value to organizational stakeholders. Thus, they are potent sources of managerial rents and hence sustained competitive advantage (Rowe, 2001). Prior research has examined various factors to explain the growth of banks, but the role of the leadership style of CEO has not been studied. Understanding relationships between performance, leadership styles, business strategies, and management systems should provide clues on how the growth paths of fast track banks differ from those of lazybones. Prior research has focused on diverse personal, bank, and market characteristics that influence small business success.

Crespi (2003) in his study argues that the attitudes and behaviors change of the leaders substantially shape the functioning of smaller banks. In fact, owner/CEOs of small businesses have a strong influence on bank functioning and overall performance. The CEO of a small business, such as a restaurant, regional real estate agency, printing and publishing bank, or even a small local beauty salon, is often the operational manager as well as the leader of the bank. These CEOs are often involved with vendors and customers. They would be in charge of financial control and reporting systems and they tend to supervise operations and handle personnel decisions. At the same time, they continue to be the CEOs who frame the bank's vision and effectuate it through strategic planning.

Hence, the leadership change, which is indicative of their tendency in managerial behaviors and actions, is an essential ingredient in the mix of factors that influence a bank's success (Avolio, 1999). A related premise underlying this study is the likelihood of a strong correlation between leadership change and bank characteristics. Specifically, it is posited that in order for a bank to succeed, the business strategies and management practices have to fit or match the owner/CEO's leadership style. In other words, certain types of business strategies and management systems are more appropriate than others for particular types of leadership styles and success is more likely when there is such an internal consistency.

Leadership change helps organizations achieve their current objectives more efficiently by linking job performance to valued rewards and by ensuring employees have the resources needed to get the job done. The level of integration and interdependencies that are needed for the new work environment as well as global

competition require leadership that goes beyond the more basic transactional styles, which involve contingent reinforcement and management by exception, to styles that are more intellectually stimulating, inspirational, and charismatic (Avolio, 1999). Further, leadership change creates a strategic vision, communicate that vision through framing and use of metaphor, model the vision by walking the talk and acting consistently, and build commitment towards the vision (McShane & Von Glinow, 2000). This view suggests that leadership change will result in high levels of cohesion, commitment, trust, motivation, and performance in these new organizational environments.

Previous empirical research and Meta analyses have indicated that leadership change has a positive effect on individual performance and organizational outcomes (Howell & Hall-Merenda, 1999). Numerous studies have reported positive relationships between leadership change and outcomes at the individual level and bank levels (Avolio, 1999; Kirkpatrick & Locke 1996). Most recently, many empirical studies have reported that leadership change has a positive impact on follower performance and bank outcomes (Avolio 2003 Jung & Sosik 2002; MacKenzie 2000; Walumbwa, 2002).

Employee Training change on Bank Performance

Improved capabilities, knowledge and skills of the talented workforce proved to be a major source of competitive advantage in a global market (McKinsey, 2006). To develop the desired knowledge, skills and abilities of the employees, to perform well on the job, requires effective training programs that may also effect employee motivation and commitment. In order to prepare their workers to do their job as desired, organizations provides training as to optimize their employee's potential. Most of the banks, by applying long term planning, invest in the building new skills by their workforce, enabling them to cope with the uncertain conditions that they may face in future, thus, improving the employee performance through superior level of motivation and commitment. When employees recognize their organization interest in them through offering training programs, they in turn apply their best efforts to achieve organizational goals, and show high performance on job.

Farooq (2011) mentioned in his study that training and development programs, as one of the vital human resource management practice, positively affects the quality of the workers knowledge, skills and capability and thus results in higher employee performance on job. This relation ultimately contributes to supreme organizational performance. The result of Farooq (2011) study depicts the positive correlation between training and employee performance as $r=.233$. Thus, the results reveal that it is not possible for the bank to gain higher returns without best utilization of its human resource, and it can only happen when bank is able to meet its employee's job related needs in timely fashion. Training is the only ways of identifying the deprived need of employees and then building their required competence level so that they may perform well to achieve organizational goals.

Moreover, the result of the study of Sultana *et al.*, (2012), conducted in telecom sector of Pakistan, states that the variation in employee performance is brought by training programs. Further, they explain that training is good predictor of employee performance. As depicted by the work of Harrison (2000), learning through training influence the organizational performance by greater employee performance, and is said to be a key factor in the achievement of corporate goals. However, implementing training programs as a solution to covering performance issues such as filling the gap between the standard and the actual performance is an effective way of improving employee performance (Swart *et al.*, 2005).

According to Swart *et al.*, (2005), bridging the performance gap refers to implementing a relevant training intervention for the sake of developing particular skills and abilities of the workers and enhancing employee performance. He further elaborate the concept by stating that training facilitate organization to recognize that its workers are not performing well and a thus their knowledge, skills and attitudes needs to be molded according

to the bank needs. There might be various reasons for poor performance of the employees such as workers may not feel motivated anymore to use their competencies, or may be not confident enough on their capabilities, or they may be facing work- life conflict. All the above aspects must be considered by the bank while selecting most appropriate training intervention that helps organization to solve all problems and enhance employee motivational level to participate and meet bank expectations by showing desired performance. As mentioned by Swart *et al.*(2005) this employee superior performance occur only because of good quality training program that leads to employee motivation and their needs fulfillment.

According to Wright & Geroy (2001), employee competencies changes through effective training programs. It not only improves the overall performance of the employees to effectively perform the current job but also enhance the knowledge, skills an attitude of the workers necessary for the future job, thus contributing to superior organizational performance. Through training the employee competencies are developed and enable them to implement the job related work efficiently, and achieve bank objectives in a competitive manner

Bakar (2003), reports that there is a positive correlation between effective training program and employee productivity, however to make it possible, (Swart *et al.*, 2005), it is the responsibility of the managers to identify the factors that hinders training program effectiveness and should take necessary measures to neutralize their effect on employee performance. In addition, Ahmad (2003), concluded that high level of employee commitment is achieved if training achieve learning outcomes and improves the performance, both on individual and organizational level. These findings are also consistent with the results of Kim (2006) research work.

Although the above literature provides the evidences regarding the benefits of training and its positive influence on employee performance, Cheramie *et al.*, (2007), argued that, management, mostly feel hesitant while investing in its human resource due to various reasons. Sometime, in spite of receiving effective and timely training programs, employee are intended to cash it for the sake of their own market value and employment opportunity , or willing to change job just because of higher salaries, and thus, bank investment in training results as a cost rather than profit. It is also observed that due to the resistance of the organization towards offering training, propels individuals to invest themselves for their career development and greater performance (Baruch, 2006).

Material and methods

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The total population was 25 banks within Nairobi CBD. From the 25 banks database, there was a total of 225head of departments. Using this formula a sample of 119 head of departments were selected. The data collection instruments used in this study was a questionnaire and interview guide. Cronbach's coefficient Alpha of more than 0.7 was taken as the cut off value for being acceptable, which enhanced the identification of the dispensable variables and deleted variables. Multiple regression analysis was applied to analyze the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent variables (Hair *et al.*, 2005). The study also utilized variable inflation factor (VIF) to handle the issue of Multi-collinearity. All the above statistical tests were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20. All tests were two-tailed. Significant levels were measured at 95% confidence level with significant differences recorded at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the findings and discussions of the data that was collected from the field based on specific objectives of the study presented in chapter one. This is done through the use of frequencies, correlation and regression. Results have been presented in such a way that they answer the research questions. A total of one

hundred and nineteen (119) questionnaires were distributed to the Heads of Department of which one hundred and two (102) were returned. The response rate for the distributed questionnaires was therefore 85.7%. The high response rates facilitated gathering sufficient data that could be generalized to determine the effect of strategic change on bank performance.

Sample Characteristics

This section presents personal information of the respondents who participated in the research study. The study deemed it important to establish the number of years the bank has been in existence. The results are as presented in table 1. Based on the results, 51% (52) of the respondents noted that the bank has been in existence for more than 5 years and 49% (50) of them stated that the bank has been in existence for a period ranging between 2 to 5 years. From the results, 52% of the respondents are between 26 to 45 years, 40.2% (41) of the respondents are over the age of 46 and 7.8% (8) of them are between 18 to 25 years. Prior research has shown that age is negatively related to the ability and willingness to learn (Colquitt et al., 2000; Kanferand Ackerman, 2004; Kubeck et al., 1996; Warr, 2001; Warr and Birdi, 1998; Yeatts et al., 2000). Basing in this assertion, majority of the respondents (between 26 to 45 years) are more likely to embrace strategic change since they comprise relatively young individuals. Finally, it was important to establish the education level held by the study respondents in order to ascertain if they were equipped with relevant knowledge and skills. As presented in table 4.1, 68.6% (70) of them are graduates, 22.5% (23) have a post-graduate degree, 7.8% (8) Diploma and 1% (1) O level. These findings implied that most of the respondents were qualified to understand the nature of the study problem. This concurs with Joppe (2000) that during research process, respondents with technical knowledge on the study problem assist in gathering reliable and accurate data on the problem under investigation.

Leadership Style Change

This section of the analysis illustrates the results on leadership style change. The results are as presented in table 1. The study sought to establish if managers are willing and able to try new things and balance risk/reward. The results were such that of the respondents agreed that managers are willing and able to try new things and balance risk/reward. Management is willing and able to fully appreciate the employees' experience of change without attaching a value judgment to it. In a bid to establish if the bank keeps managers who bring new changes to the bank, the respondents were asked on their opinion on the same. The results revealed that the bank keeps managers who bring new changes to the bank and that it has not been fully established if the bank immediately fires leaders who do not bring back change to the bank. From the preceding results, it is undefined whether the bank regularly changes its customers

Table 1 Leadership Style Change

	Mean	Std. Deviation
We have experienced change in leadership	2.73	0.924
The banks regularly change it managers	2.92	1.078
The bank keeps managers who bring new changes to the bank	3.44	1.165
The bank immediately fires leaders who do not bring change to the bank	3.21	1.146
Managers are willing and able to fully appreciate another person's experience of change and to not attach a value judgment to it	3.49	0.805
Managers are willing and able to try new things and balance risk/reward	3.71	0.765
Leadership Style Change	3.16	0.567

Source: (Field Data, 2016)

In general, results on leadership style change summed up to a mean of 3.16 and a standard deviation of 0.567. The results suggest that it is undefined whether the bank keeps managers that bring change to the bank, if the bank immediately fires leaders who do not bring back change to the bank, if the bank regularly changes its customers and whether the bank has experienced change in leadership. Despite this, the leadership in place is flexible and willing to make changes to meet the conditions in the business environment. Also, the management is willing and able to fully appreciate the employees' experience of change without attaching a value judgment to it.

Employees Training Change

This section of the analysis presents the results on employee training change. Table 2 illustrates the results. In an attempt to establish whether the bank allows new innovative ideas among new employees, the respondents were asked for their opinion. Generally, the results on employees training change summed up to a mean of 3.826 and a standard deviation of 0.832 an indication that the banks allow new innovative ideas among new employees, encourages creativity among employees, regularly hires new employees with expertise in different areas and ensures employees are regularly trained to bring new change to the firm. As mentioned by Swart *et al.* (2005) this employee superior performance occur only because of good quality training program that leads to employee motivation and their needs fulfillment.

Table 2 Employees Training Change

	Mean	Std. Deviation
The bank allow new innovative ideas among new employees	3.5	1.124
The bank encourage creativity among employees	3.95	1.047
The bank regularly hire new employee with expertise in different areas	3.71	1.04
The bank ensure employees are regularly trained to bring new change to the firm	4.15	0.959
Employees Training Change	3.826	0.832

Source: (Field Data, 2016)

Firm Performance

The study sought to establish the performance of the commercial banks. The results are as presented in table 4.9. The performance of the firms was sought over a 4 year period right from the year 2012 to 2015. From the findings, there has been a significant decline in the sales volume from a high of 3,924,001.00 in the year 2012 with a slight decline to 3,779,265.00 in 2013 and the least being 1,591,245.00 in 2015. The net profit is also the highest in 2012 and lowest in 2015. Moreover, the result of the study of Sultana *et al.*, (2012), conducted in telecom sector of Pakistan, states that the variation in employee performance is brought by training programs. Further, they explain that training is good predictor of employee performance. As depicted by the work of Harrison (2000), learning through training influence the organizational performance by greater employee performance, and is said to be a key factor in the achievement of corporate goals. However, implementing training programs as a solution to covering performance issues such as filling the gap between the standard and the actual performance is an effective way of improving employee performance (Swart *et al.*, 2005).

Firm performance is used as one indicator of effectiveness for small and large businesses and is a fundamental concern of many practicing managers. Ultimately, success and growth will be gauged by how well a firm does

relative to the goals it has set for itself and as Sababu (2007) states; the formal strategic management systems significantly influence organizational performance.

Table 3 Firm Performance

		Return on asset (ROA)	Sale volume	Net profit	Customer base in “millions”
2015	Mean	0.501	1,591,245.00	1,500,000	3.5
	SD	0.119	238,445.00	204,480	1.6
2014	Mean	1.127	3,424,770.00	2,270,133	3.2
	SD	0.644	109,621.00	10,788	2.2
2013	Mean	1.4047	3,779,265.00	2,822,478	2.9
	SD	0.931	98,401.00	12,411	2.4
2012	Mean	1.881	3,924,001.00	2,970,193	2.9
	SD	0.74	113,400.00	99,681	1.1

Source: (Field Data, 2016)

Various studies have been carried out on the effects of strategic management practices on performance. These studies range from regional, national and international. Ofunya and Afande (2013), studied on the effects of strategic management practices on performance of financial institutions in Kenya. They Found out that outstanding customer service, improving operational efficiency, controlling quality of products and services, intense supervision of frontline personnel, developing brand or company name identification, targeting a specific market niche or segment and providing specialty products and services. In this study the researcher looked at the financial institutions that whose customers are driven by the zeal to accumulate wealth by growing their investments. Kathama (2012), studied strategic planning practices and performance of state corporations in Kenya and found that there is a positive relationship between strategic planning process and performance of corporations.

Hypothesis testing

Table 4 presents Pearson correlation results of the study dependent and independent variables to assess the association of the variables. Findings revealed that leadership style change was positively and significantly correlated to firm performance ($r = 0.667$, $\rho < 0.01$). Also, employee training change was indicated to positively relate with firm performance ($r = 0.721$, $\rho < 0.01$). This implies leadership style change, and employee training change are expected to influence firm performance,

According to table 4, the R value indicates a relatively strong correlation between predictor variables and the consequent variable (firm performance). This is because the R value is positive (.812). This means that firm performance that the studied commercial banks recorded was attributed to a certain percentage of predictor variables. According to the value of the R-Square, 65.9% of the firm performance could be explained by independent variables. Therefore independent variables would have a 65.9% influence on the performance of the studied commercial banks while the remaining 34.1% could be attributed to other factors other than predictor variables.

Research findings also showed that leadership style change had coefficients of estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_2 = 0.237$ (p -value = 0.005 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) implying leadership style change has a significant effect on firm performance. Cognate to the results, Crespi (2003) in his study argues that owner/CEOs of small businesses have a strong influence on bank functioning and overall performance.

Similarly, Avolio, (1999) notes that leadership style change is an essential ingredient in the mix of factors that influence a bank's success. The results are also in tally with that of McShane & Von Glinow, (2000) indicating that leadership change creates a strategic vision, communicate the vision through framing and use of metaphor hence improving the overall firm performance.

Finally, findings showed that employee training change had coefficients of estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_4 = 0.407$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$) thus we fail to accept the hypothesis and conclude that employee training change has a significant effect on firm performance. This suggests that there is up to 0.407 unit increase in firm performance for each unit increase in employee training change. The effect of employee training change is four times the effect attributed to the error, this is indicated by the t-test value = 4.846. This conforms to a study by Farooq (2011) indicating that training and development programs positively affects the quality of the workers knowledge, skills and capability and thus results in higher employee performance on job. The results also corroborate with that of Sultana *et al.*, (2012) indicating that the variation in employee performance is brought by training programs.

Table 4 correlation and regression results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	zero order correlation	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	-1.048	0.444		-2.362	0.02			
Leadership Style Change	0.329	0.115	0.237	2.846	0.005	.667**	0.507	1.974
Employee straining change	0.508	0.105	0.407	4.846	0	.721**	0.499	2.005
R Square	0.659							
Adjusted R Square	0.645							

a Dependent Variable: firm performance

Conclusions and Recommendations

Leadership style change helps banks to achieve their objectives by linking job performance to value rewards and ensuring that the resources required to meet the said objectives are available. As such, the leadership style change facilitates the improvement of performance. This is especially the case when the bank's strategies are in line with the leadership style in place. Also, leaders and subordinates can also influence each other in order to achieve organizational goals. For instance, when the leaders are willing to fully appreciate another person's experience of change and to not attach a value judgment to it, improved bank performance is realized. Set objectives are realized, employees are motivated and there is implementation of strategy. As such, leadership style change positively influences bank performance.

Training change is crucial since it increases employees' level of understanding on the job they are tasked with. Specifically, it is pivotal to the realization of high output levels in the bank. In the event that employees recognize the organization has interest in them through offering training programs, they are likely to apply their best efforts to achieve organizational goals thus enhancing organizational performance.

The study has established that leadership style change is a key driving force for improved bank performance. It plays a role in enhancing or retarding the interest and commitment of the individuals in the organization. Therefore, it is utmost necessary for managers to be willing to fully appreciate person's experience of change and to not attach a value judgment to it. They also need to be willing and able to try new things and balance risk/reward. The leadership in place should be a source of motivation to the employees, lead to realization of objectives and the implementation of strategy.

employee training change has exhibited a positive and significant influence on the performance of commercial banks. There is therefore need for employee training so that they can develop the appropriate knowledge and skills to work efficiently, and achieve bank objectives. Also, banks need to allow new ideas among new employees and encourage creativity among them. In addition, banks should engage in hiring new employees with expertise in different areas and ensure that they are regularly trained.

Despite the in-depth coverage of this study and its findings, there still exists a gap that future research could explore. This study only focused on the firm performance of commercial banks but firm performance is quite wide. Therefore, the study suggests that further research should focus on other performance measures such as internal business process, learning and growth and customers.

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